

MENTAL HEALTH OF RURAL ADOLESCENT SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SOUTH 24 PARGANA DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to find out the level of mental health of rural adolescent school students in South 24 Pargana District of West Bengal. The data were collected from 140 samples (70 Boys & 70 Girls). The researcher used the standardized Mental Health Inventory (MHI) with six dimensions developed by Jagdish & Srivastava (1986), through purposive sampling technique. Mean, S.D, and t-test statistical techniques were employed to analysis and interpret the results. The major findings of the study is that there is no significant difference between mean scores of boys and girls adolescents students.

Keywords: Mental Health, Rural Adolescent, South 24 Pargana District.

INTRODUCTION

Mental health is the emotional and spiritual resilience that allows one to enjoy life and to survive pain, suffering and disappoint (Panchal, 2013). It is a positive sense of well-being and an underlying belief in one's own and others' dignity and worth. Mental health is about how a person thinks, feels, and acts when faced with life's situations. Mental health is how people look at themselves, their lives, and the other people in their lives; evaluate their challenges and problems; and explores choices. This includes handling stress, relating to other people, and making decisions (Panchal, 2013). Pramod kumar (1991) states that mental health is an indicator which shows a person's ability to meet social, emotional, physical, psychological demands.

According to world health organization (WHO), the individuals who are in the age between 10-19 years are adolescents. It is the most critical transitions phase in one's life span which is characterized by tremendous growth and potential. At this stage established behavior patterns of the adolescents have long lasting effects on the mental health and well being, that may be positive or negative. At the global level, it is estimated that approx. 20% of youth experience mental health problems each year (Kessler, 2005). Adolescents bear a greatest risk of mental health problems during their transition stage i.e. from childhood to adulthood (Kessler & others, 2005).

Recent studies have identified 'Depression' as a mental problem among various problems of adolescents (WHO). World health organization (WHO) is also strengthening the mental health services provisions by implementing the Mental Health Gap Action Programme (MHGAP). Adolescents face internal conflicts which directly affects their mental health and adjustment in the society. Mental health is major area of attention development (WHO, 2010). It is perceived as an asset to develop individually, socially as well as economically (WHO, 2004). The increase in mental health issues is a growing concern for the educators in recent time. Research has exhibited that there is an increase in the case of depression and other mental health issues among adolescents (WHO, 2012).

Srivastava et al. (1999) studied on 'A study of Mental Health of Hindi and English medium students' the mental health of 80 students studying 11th and 12th standard from English medium and Hindi medium schools located at Haridwar. The result showed that Hindi medium student had better mental health in comparison to English medium students. The authors also reported that symptoms of egocentrism and emotional instability in English medium students were high in comparison to Hindi medium students. They suggested that parents and teachers should cooperate each-other in solving the problems.

Arulkumar & William (2017) in their paper entitled 'A study of mental health of high school students in Thiruvavur District'. The data were collected from Thiruvavur educational district. The investigator used the Mental Health Inventory, developed by Jagadish and Srivastava (Revised 1996). Around 10% of the students have high level of mental health and 1/3 of total students have average mental health. No significant differences have been found in the mean score of the mental health among the subgroup of students based on their gender, residence and type of schools in which they were studying.

Roul & Bihari (2015) studied on 'Mental health of School going boys and girls adolescents in Secondary School of Delhi'; the study was designed to evaluate the mental health of school going adolescents in secondary schools of East Delhi. The finding of this study is that there is no significant difference between mean scores of boys and girls adolescents on the different dimensions of mental health in secondary schools; and 2) there is no significant difference between mean scores of boys and girls adolescents on the overall mental health dimensions in secondary schools.

Shokeen (2017) in his research article entitled, 'A study of mental health and social adjustment of Senior Secondary students' attempts to explore the mental health and social adjustment of the senior secondary students of Delhi. He also made an attempt to elaborate the relationship between mental health and social adjustment of adolescents. The researcher used Mental Health Battery of Arun Kumar Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta's and Social Adjustment Inventory of Dr. R.C. Deva for the sample subjects. The findings

reveal a positive and significant relationship between the Mental Health and Social Adjustment among the adolescents.

Lal, Sharma & kumar (2013) in their research paper entitled, 'A study of Mental Health and Socio Economic Status among Youth'; made an attempt to explore the mental health and socio economic status of the youth in Chandigarh. The participants were well informed about the purpose of the study and also assured about their confidentiality. The Mental Health Inventory (Jagdish and Srivastava, 1983) has been used to quantify the study and their socioeconomic status was measured with the help of family income. The statistically analyzed result corroborates that subjects of high income family possess good mental health as compared to the low income participants.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The researcher has taken into consideration the following objectives:

- To study the significant difference between mean scores of rural adolescent school students on the basis of age.
- To study the significant difference between mean scores of rural adolescent school students on the basis of religion.
- To study the significant difference between mean scores of rural adolescent school students on the basis of birth order.
- To study the significant difference between mean scores of rural adolescent school students on the basis of father occupation status.
- To study the significant difference between mean scores of rural adolescent school students on the basis of family monthly income.

HYPOTHESES

- Ho1: There is no significant mean difference of mental health among rural adolescent school students on the basis of age.
- Ho2: There is no significant mean difference of mental health among rural adolescent school students on the basis of religion.
- Ho3: There is no significant mean difference of mental health among rural adolescent school students on the basis of birth order.
- Ho4: There is no significant mean difference of mental health among rural adolescent school students on the basis of father occupation status.
- Ho5: There is no significant mean difference of mental health among rural adolescent school students on the basis of family monthly income.

METHODOLOGY

Local of the Study

The study was conducted in a rural area in South 24 Parganas District.

Sample and sampling technique:

The target population of this study was all the rural adolescent school students. The researcher investigated 140 school students (70 boys & 70 girls). Purposive sampling technique has been used for data collection. In this sampling technique, the investigator select the all sample based on his own judgment and experience. A purposive sample is the one arbitrarily selected because there is good evidence that it is very representative of the total population (Guilford). The purposive sampling technique is the deliberate choice of an informant due the qualities the informant possesses. It is a nonrandom technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of informants. The researcher decides what needs to be known and sets out to fine people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience (Bernard, 2002).

Table 1: Variables & Sample Distribution

Variables	Standard	Number	Mean	Percentage
Age	14-16 Year	60	136.04	42.85
	17-19 Year	80	137.44	57.14
Religion	Hindu	70	138.88	50.00
	Muslim	70	137.09	50.00
Birth Order	1 st -2 nd	67	136.56	47.85
	3 rd and Above	73	135.43	52.14
Father Occupation Status	Farmer	90	139.77	64.28
	Labor	50	136.03	35.71
Family Monthly Income	Below 8000	87	138.36	62.14
	9000 and Above	53	135.79	37.85

Tool/ instrument used:

It is descriptive survey study. The data were collected from the 140 samples (70 Boys & 70 Girls) by using tool/ instrument like Mental Health Inventory (MHI), (Jagadish and Srivastava, 1986). The inventory consisted of 56 items and each item was rated on 4-point rating scale ranging from always to never, with 4 score to Always; 3 score to Often; 2 score to Rarely; and 1 score to Never marked response as to be assigned for true keyed (positive) statement where as 1, 2, 3, and 4 scores, for Always to Never respectively in case of false keyed (negative) statements. Inventory comprises of six dimensions such as, Positive Self-Evaluation (PSE), Perception of Reality (PR), Integration of Personality (IP), Autonomy (A), Group Oriented Attitude (GOA), and Environmental Mastery (EM). The split-half reliability of the scale was found to be .73 and the construct validity of the

scale was found to be .54. High score obtained by subject is indicative of good mental health and low score indicated of poor mental health.

Statistical Techniques

Based on the nature of data collection through Mental Health Inventory (MHI), mean, SD, and 't'-test statistical techniques were employed to analysis and interpret the results. The data were analyzed by the investigator through SPSS.

RESULT & INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA

Table 2: The Data Analyze on The Basis of Age

Variables	Standard	Number	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remark
Age	14-16 year	60	136.04	12.20	59	2.08	Sig
	17-19 year	80	137.44	13.76	79		

Interpretation: The result in table 2 indicates that the calculate 't' value 2.08 is larger than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significant in 59 & 79 degree of freedom, so the hypotheses is accepted. Hence the result revealed that there were significant differences between the age group of 14-16 year and 17-19 in rural adolescent learners.

Table 3: The Data Analyze on the Basis of Religion

Variables	Standard	Number	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remark
Religion	Hindu	70	138.88	13.04	69	1.73	Not sig
	Muslim	70	137.09	13.86	69		

Interpretation: The result from the table 3 indicates that the calculate 't' value 1.73 is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significant in 69 & 69 degree of freedom, so the hypotheses is not accepted. It shows that there is significant difference in mean score but this is not high, of rural adolescent learner's mental health on the basis of religion.

Table 4: The Data Analyze on the Basis of Birth Order

Variables	Standard	Number	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remark
Birth order	1 st -2 nd	67	136.56	11.41	66	0.97	Not sig
	3 rd and above	73	135.43	10.84	72		

Interpretation: The result in table 4 indicates that the calculate 't' value 0.97 is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significant in 66 & 72 degree of freedom, so the hypotheses is not accepted. Hence the result revealed that there were significant mean differences between the rural adolescent learners according to their birth order.

Table 5: The Data Analyze on The Basis of Father Occupation Status

Variabes	Standard	Number	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remark
Father Occupation Status	Farmer	90	139.77	14.01	89	2.09	Sig
	Labor	50	136.03	12.55	49		

Interpretation: The result in table 5, shows that the calculate ‘t’ value 2.09 is larger than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significant in 89 & 49 degree of freedom, so the hypotheses is accepted. It has been observed that there is significant difference in mean score of rural adolescent learner’s mental health on the basis of their father’s occupational status.

Table 6: the data analyze on the basis of their family monthly income

Variables	Standard	Number	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Remark
Family Monthly Income	Below 8000	87	138.36	15.05	86	1.47	Not sig
	9000 and above	53	135.79	12.47	52		

Interpretation: As above mentioned in table 6, indicates that the calculate ‘t’ value 1.47 is less than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significant in 86 & 52 degree of freedom, so the hypotheses is rejected. Hence, the result revealed that there are significant differences in mean score of rural adolescent learners on the basis of their family monthly income.

DISCUSSION & FINDINGS

From the result we get some important points that post adolescent (17-19 years) rural students were better in mental health status than pre adolescent (14-16) rural students. Although mean score are not highly significantly different, according to their age. On the basis of religion, we found that the students who belong to Hindu families are better in psychological wellbeing than the Islam students, but this difference is not significant. Gajjar & Ksaji (2015) found no significant differences in the mental health of the Hindu and Muslim people. In the light of birth order, we observed significant difference between 1st-2nd & 3rd and above rural students and the result is not significant. Father’s occupational status is very important factor in the field of psychological wellbeing. Farmer family’s adolescent learners (M=139.77) are better in mental health than the adolescent students (136.03) whose father is labor. Another important effective variable is monthly income. In the present study, we show that the family whose monthly income is within 8000 rupees (Indian), they successfully controlled their psychological needs than the family with high income (9000 Rupees & above).

CONCLUSION

In the present circumstances, youth are facing difficulties in life. These difficulties are ascending to many psycho-somatic problems such as mental illness, anxiety, tension, frustration and emotional upset in day to day life. It is evident that the rural adolescent school students have different level of mental health. There is no age, birth order, occupation status, monthly income, exist in the mental health among school students, and all do not have the same level of mental health. These students have low level of mental health, who are continuously being ignore by the family members, school and community. So, it is very needful to conduct various effective programme to develop mental health to those students.

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